

Uttarayan is Festival of colourful kites result into death of speechless birds

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Introduction

Uttarayan, also known as the Kite festival, is one of the biggest festivals celebrated in India. The festival of Makar Sankranti and therefore uttarayan, falls on the fourteenth of January every year. It is also called the festival of uttarayan because on this day Uttarayan starts taking place while marking the arrival of spring and the transition of the sun into the Makara rashi (the Capricorn). In quite a few states in India, Makar Sankranti is considered as a major harvest festival. Its significance lies in its commemoration of goddess Sankranti's triumph over evil and the brutal rakshasa sankarasur (demon), who would torture and kill humans.

Uttarayan is celebrated mainly throughout Gujarat, Rajasthan and Central India. The main event, which is the international kite festival, is hosted in Ahmedabad and attracts participants and spectators from all over the globe.

It is also a festival where people come together in celebration and bury their hatchets, offering each other sweets in a joyous atmosphere. In this article, you will read all about the kite flying festival in India and hit us up to witness this spectacle in person. Throughout the festival week, markets are flooded with kite sellers or patang. It remains operative 24x7 during the festival weeks and is always crowded with sellers selling all sorts of high-quality kites and buyers buying in bulk. Most of these kites are handmade with bamboo shoots and thin paper. Following the general rituals, devotees, especially the farmers, worship Lord Surya or the sun god seeking blessings for a productive harvest season. People wear new clothes, eat traditional cuisines and spend time with their families. An important part of the uttaryan festival is flying kites. On this day, individuals of all ages get their hands on the manjha and the sky gets decorated with a variety of colorful kites.

Figure-1 Shows injure of bird during kite festival by manjha

The most common game played on uttarayan, kite fighting is played by using one's kite string to tear down someone else's. Small, unstable kites are used and controlled solely with the tension in the line. Thin cotton or hemp line is used to fly a kite. Before the flight, however, the line is coated with a mixture of crushed glass and glue known as Manjha. After applying the manjha to the line, it becomes abrasive and with correct technique, can be used to tear other lines during flight. The lines are often so sharp that they cut fingers. Usually, there are teams of two, with one player holding the spool and the other feeding the line through their fingers, controlling the tension. When the line is left taut, the kite gets deformed by the wind and remains stable to some extent. By reducing the tension, it begins to sway left or right depending on the wind. Players use this phenomenon to attack their opponents. Bridle position, spine curve, and center of gravity, all play essential roles in flight control. On cutting down another kite, the victor yells and often drums are sounded. Kite fighting is an enjoyable sport, both to

After a series of unfortunate incidents during kite flying competitions, make injuries in several speechless animals and birds. The “chines manjha” is sharp and deep cuts the neck, wings, legs, nerve injuries, fractures, dislocations and sometime serious blood loss cause death of birds.

Due to fractures and nerve injure bird leads to temporary and permeant disability.

Do

- ❖ The banned the sale of the “chines manjha”.
- ❖ Use cotton tried in state of manjha.
- ❖ If birds found to injured than as soon as possible to bring it.
- ❖ veterinary care nearby veterinary hospital.
- ❖ Try to give first aid to the bird’s rescue facilities and camps are built in various different state of India during Makar Sankranti to take care of wounded birds during kite flying. People are required to be informed of how to reach these rescue

groups and veterinary doctors in case of an emergency.

Don't

- ❖ The usage of Chinese manja is prohibited. Kites and kite strings have the potential to act as electrical conductors. So, flying kites over power lines with high voltage should be avoided.
- ❖ To avoid fly kite during early morning and evening during most of bird movement
- ❖ Avoid use of chines manjha.
- ❖ To avoid kites flying near birds' nests.

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